

STUDY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOOD FLOUR COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Plasma surface coating method was applied to the wood flour to improve its bonding and dispersion with the polypropylene. Some mechanical test results and visual inspection indicates the good compatibility between the wood powder and the PP and relatively good interfacial adhesion between wood flour and PP matrix was seen. Also, this method is considered as a non-toxic process as compared to other direct chemical method.

KEYWORDS: wood flour, atmospheric glow discharger, plasma polymerization, extruder, Pellets, wood flour composite.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous researches have been performed recently to develop wood flour and/or fiber reinforced polymers due to low cost, renewability, biodegradability, abundance and high specific strength and stiffness of wood fiber [1-5]. However, the compounding of wood flour or fiber with a polymer matrix (such as polypropylene, PP) often leads to poor mechanical properties of composites. The poor mechanical properties of wood flour reinforced PP composites are due to (1) poor compatibility between the polar hydrophilic wood flour or fiber and the non-polar hydrophobic PP, with weak interfacial adhesion between wood flour or fiber and PP matrix. And (2) poor dispersion of wood flour and fiber in the PP matrix.

A new environmental friendly method of fabricating wood flour composite is developed. This method utilizes non toxic chemical bonding agent. Wood flour is dried and coated with hexamethyl-disiloxane, methane and benzene in a closed chamber before it is mixed with PP (Hanwha Co.) to produce pellets by an extruder.

50wt% of the wood flour composite coupons were produced for testing since wood flour composites containing at least 50wt% of wood flour is defined as a wood.

CONTINUOUS PROCESS OF DRYING AND SURFACE COATING

As shown in Fig 1, the wood flour was dried in an atmospheric glow discharge (AGD) reactor composed of vacuum and heater. Helium was used as a carrier gas and hexamethyl-disiloxane [HMDSO], methane and benzene were used to modify surface property by plasma polymerisation [6]. The electrodes were inductively connected around the tube and the frequency and the voltage were 20KHz and 3 KV respectively. The contact angles of coated

polymers are measured by a goniometer. Table 1 summarizes the contact angles and calculated surface energies for various chemicals. HMDSO was chosen since it is most lipophilic due to its lowest polar surface energy. The surface energies may be calculated by

$$r_{SL} = r_{SL} + r_{LV} - 2(r_S^d r_{LV}^d)^{1/2} - 2(r_S^p r_{LV}^p)^{1/2}. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1: Continuous Process of Drying and Surface Coating of Wood Flour

The average moisture content in the Wood flour was about 8% of moisture before drying and about 2-3% after drying. The average particle size was $138.22 \mu\text{m}$ [min= $28.86 \mu\text{m}$, max = $346.86 \mu\text{m}$] and the density was 1.5084 g/cm^3 before drying. The treated wood flour was mixed with PP powder mechanically before producing pellets by PRISM TSE 16 TC (Thermo Electron Corp.) twin screw extruder[Fig. 2]. The pellets are molded to form mechanical test coupons for 10 minutes at 195°C and 10 kgf/mm^2 pressure.

10 to 50wt% of the wood flour were mixed with PP. The tensile tests results indicate that the wood flour was quite evenly dispersed within the PP matrix. This may be due to the enhancement of compatibility of the particles within a matrix.

Fig. 2: Producing Wood flour and PP pellets by PRISM TSE 16 TC

Table 1: Contact Angles and Calculated surface energy

Sample	Contact angle(°)		Surface Energy (dyne/cm)		
	Water	Glycerol	Total	Dispersion	Polar
Oxygen-PET	8	9	73.73	12.78	60.96
Benzene-PET	58.8	65	49.17	1.08	47.37
CH4-PET	55.7	47.6	59.56	2.14	57.42
Acrylic acid-PET	35.7	47.7	71.94	1.72	70.22
Hexafluoroethane-PET	93	103	28.75	0.54	28.21
Trifluorotolune-PET	49	53.1	53.81	4.90	48.91
HMDSO*	105	76	74.77	71.68	3.09

* HMDSO : Hexamethyl-disiloxane

Mechanical Test

Tensile tests and 3-point bending tests are carried out according to ASTM D638(Type V) and ASTM D790, respectively. Tensile test results are shown in Fig. 3 and 3-point bending test results are shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 is the work done by Chungnam National University in Korea and is for comparison.

From Fig. 3 and 4, it can be noticed that the data are fairly even around the average values. This may indicate that the wood flours are evenly distributed within the wood composites. When comparing the data in Fig. 3 and Fig. 5, the tensile strength for 50 weight percentage wood flour containing composite is quite close to that of PP and is higher compared to 45% wood flour containing composite. This may indicate that present method provided better bonding between the wood flour and PP.

Fig. 3: Tensile test results for wood composite containing 50wt% wood flour

Fig. 4: 3 point bending test results for wood composite containing 50wt% wood flour

Fig. 5: Data from Chemical Eng. Dept. Chungnam U., J. of Korea Ind. & Eng. Chemistry, Vol. 10, No. 1, February 1999, pp. 46-50.

Visual Inspection

Fig. 6 represents the 10wt% wood flour within PP. It may be seen that the plasma surface coated wood flours are fairly evenly dispersed.

Fig. 6: 10wt% of wood flour within PP

In above pictures, lighter region represent PP. In 9(a), It can be seen that the wood flours are dispersed quite evenly while, in (b), the wood flours are sort of bunched up here and there and voids are also detected (circle).

Conclusions

- o Non toxic surface treatment methodology was introduced. The good compatibility between the wood powder and the PP and relatively good interfacial adhesion between wood powder and PP matrix was seen.
- o The moisture content in the Wood flour was about 8% before drying and was about 2-3% after drying.
- o The average particle size was $138.22\mu\text{m}$ [min= $28.86\mu\text{m}$, max= $346.86\mu\text{m}$] and the density was 1.5084 g/cm^3 before drying.
- o Molding conditions to form a tensile specimen was 10 minutes at 195°C and 10 kgf/mm^2 pressure.
- o The mechanical tests results indicate that the wood powder was quite evenly dispersed within the PP matrix. This may be due to the enhancement of compatibility of the particles within a matrix.

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